

KOSTANECKI-ROBINSON ACYLATION OF 8-PROPIONYL- AND 8-BUTYRYL- UMBELLIFERONES

BY D. N. SHAH AND S. J. CONTRACTOR

The *o*-hydroxyacylcoumarins, described earlier (*this Journal*, 1959, 36, 679) have been found useful as starting materials for the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds like dicoumarins, chromonocoumarins and furanocoumarins. The Kostanecki-Robinson acylation of 7-hydroxy-8-propionyl- and 8-butyrylⁿ-coumarins has been effected using (i) acetic anhydride and sodium acetate, (ii) acetic anhydride and sodium phenylacetate, and (iii) propionic anhydride and sodium propionate.

7-Hydroxy-8-propionylcoumarin (I : R=Me) on treatment with acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium acetate gave a product, to which the structure, 4'-ethylcoumarino-5' : 6'-(8 : 7)- α -pyrone (II : R=Me; R'=H) has been assigned as it develops no colour with ethanolic ferric chloride, and on treatment with sodium ethoxide it is recovered unchanged.

The same coumarin (I: R=Me) on treatment with acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium phenylacetate under the condition of the Kostanecki-Robinson reaction afforded a product which showed no ferric chloride colour test; it was recovered unchanged on treatment with sodium ethoxide or alkali. Hence it has been assigned the structure, 4'-ethyl-3'-phenylcoumarino-5' : 6'-(8 : 7)- α -pyrone (II : R=Me ; R'=Ph).

Further, the Kostanecki-Robinson acylation of (I : R = Me), using propionic anhydride and fused sodium propionate, furnished a product which on similar grounds has been assigned the structure, 4'-ethyl-3'-methylcoumarino-5' : 6'-(8 : 7)- α -pyrone.

7-Hydroxy-8-butyrylⁿcoumarin (I : R=Et) was subjected to the Kostanecki-Robinson acylation using acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate. The product obtained has been assigned the structure, 4'-propylcoumarino-5' : 6'-(8 : 7)- α -pyrone (II : R=Et; R'=H) as it remains unchanged on treatment with alkali and sodium ethoxide.

The keto-coumarin (I : R=Et) on similar treatment with (i) sodium phenylacetate and acetic anhydride, and (ii) sodium propionate and propionic anhydride also afforded only one product in each case. These have been assigned the structure : 3'-phenyl-4'-propylcoumarino-5' : 6'-(8 : 7)- α -pyrone (II : R=Et ; R'=Ph) and 3'-methyl-4'-propylcoumarino-5' : 6'-(8 : 7)- α -pyrone (II : R=Et ; R'=Me) respectively on grounds similar to above.

EXPERIMENTAL

(i) *4'-Ethylcoumarino-5':6'-(8:7)- α -pyrone*.—7-Hydroxy-8-propionylcoumarin (2.2 g., 1 M), acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) and fused sodium acetate (3 g.) were refluxed for 10 hours at 160-70° (CaCl₂-guard tube). After cooling, the reaction mixture was treated with ice; the solid separating was collected, washed with water, and crystallised from acetic acid in thin brown needles, m.p. 276°, yield 0.95 g. (Found: C, 69.38; H, 4.15. C₁₄H₁₀O₄ requires C, 69.42; H, 4.16%).

Action of Alkali.—To the above coumarino- α -pyrone (0.5 g.), dissolved in ethanol, 5% NaOH solution (10 c.c.) was added, and the mixture refluxed for 1 hour on a water bath. The resulting solution was filtered hot, and cooled. On neutralising the filtrate with cold HCl a solid separated. It was collected, washed with water, and crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 276° (mixed m.p. with the original product remained undepressed).

(ii) *4'-Ethyl-3'-phenylcoumarino-5':6'-(8:7)- α -pyrone* was similarly prepared from 7-hydroxy-8-propionylcoumarin (2.2 g., 1 M) by refluxing it with acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) in presence of fused sodium phenylacetate (3 g.) at 160-70° for 8 hours. The product, isolated as above, was crystallised from acetone in pale yellow needles, m.p. 275°, yield 1.0 g. (Found: C, 75.41; H, 4.42. C₂₀H₁₄O₄ requires C, 75.46; H, 4.43%).

(iii) *4'-Ethyl-3'-methylcoumarino-5':6'-(8:7)- α -pyrone*.—7-Hydroxy-8-propionylcoumarin (2.2 g., 1 M) was similarly subjected to the Kostanecki-Robinson reaction by refluxing it with propionic anhydride (10 c.c.) and fused sodium propionate (4 g.) at 160-70° for 8 hours. The product, isolated as before, was crystallised from acetone in shining short yellow needles, m.p. 230°, yield 0.9 g. (Found: C, 70.26; H, 4.71. C₁₅H₁₂O₄ requires C, 70.30; H, 4.72%).

For sake of brevity, the products obtained from 7-hydroxy-8-butylⁿcoumarin are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Compounds.	M.P.	Cryst. form and solvent.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
4'-Propyl-CP*	240°	Brown needles (acetic acid)	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₄	C: 70.25% H: 4.70	70.30% 4.72
4'-Propyl-3'-phenyl-CP	230°	Yellow needles (acetone)	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₄	C: 75.80 H: 4.84	75.89 4.85
4'-Propyl-3'-methyl-CP	212°	Needles (acetone)	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₄	C: 71.08 H: 5.21	71.10 5.22

*CP denotes coumarino-5':6'-(8:7)- α -pyrone.

The work described in this paper was carried out in the Chemistry Department of M. G. Science Institute, Ahmedabad-9. The authors thank the Ahmedabad Education Society for facilities, and Dr. N. M. Shah for his interest and helpful suggestions during the course of the work.